

Pre-Analysis Plan:
Quantity Pricing in Rich and Poor Neighbourhoods: Evidence from
New Zealand Supermarkets

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1. Introduction

This study aims to do two things. First, it wants to document quantity pricing (surcharges or discounts) in supermarkets located in rich and poor neighbourhoods in New Zealand. Second, it wants to test whether shoppers in rich neighbourhoods in New Zealand are more likely to be subject to a quantity surcharge compared to shoppers in poor neighbourhoods.

2. Background

Quantity surcharges—where buying in larger sizes does not lead to lower unit prices—are a well-documented pricing phenomenon, occurring in 10% to 30% of product-size comparisons across multiple countries and time periods (Spratt et al, 2003). Despite growing evidence of these tactics, little research has examined how they vary by consumer demographics, especially income. Binkley et al (2003) found that time-poor U.S. shoppers were less likely to compare unit prices, making them more vulnerable to surcharges. Goel et al (2024) found in Indian retail markets that bulk-size surcharges are particularly common in areas with low competition and high-income inequality, where large-package purchases are more frequent. This study adds to the existing literature by testing whether quantity surcharges are more prevalent in wealthier versus poorer neighbourhoods in New Zealand.

3. Planned Analysis

3.1 Summary statistics about quantity pricing in rich and poor neighbourhoods

We define *quantity discount* as for product type i (e.g. milk) in supermarket s as:

$$\bullet \quad \text{Discount}\%_{is} = \left(\frac{\text{PricePerUnit}_{\text{small}} - \text{PricePerUnit}_{\text{large}}}{\text{PricePerUnit}_{\text{small}}} \right) \cdot 100$$

A **quantity surcharge** is defined as a negative quantity discount (i.e., when the unit price increases with package size).

For each neighbourhood type (rich vs. poor), we will report the following:

- The **share of product types** that show a quantity surcharge (i.e., where the quantity discount is negative).

- The **average quantity discount**, where negative values indicate surcharges.

3.2 Difference between rich and poor neighbourhoods

To test whether shoppers in rich neighbourhoods are more likely to have to pay a quantity surcharge, we estimate the following

$$Surchargedummy_{is} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 RichNeighbourhood_s + u_{is},$$

Where:

- $Surchargedummy_{is}=1$ if product i in store s has a quantity surcharge (i.e., a negative quantity discount); 0 otherwise.
- $RichNeighbourhood_s=1$ if store s is located in a **rich neighbourhood**, defined as one in the **bottom 20%** of NZ Deprivation scores **and** with a **median household income above \$124,000**. It equals 0 if the store is in a poor neighbourhood, defined as one in the top 20% of NZ Deprivation scores and with median household income below \$70,000. It is missing for stores not classified as either rich or poor.

The coefficient α_1 captures the difference in the share of products with a surcharge between rich and poor neighbourhoods. We do **not interpret this as a causal effect**. Rather, it describes a **population-level association** across all product types for which a quantity surcharge could occur in rich and poor supermarkets in New Zealand. Standard errors will be clustered at the **supermarket level**.

We also test whether the magnitude of quantity discounts differs between rich and poor neighbourhoods by estimating the following model:

$$Discount\%_{is} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RichNeighbourhood_s + \epsilon_{is},$$

where the β_1 captures the average difference in the size of the quantity surcharge between rich and poor neighbourhoods in New Zealand.

4. Data Collection Strategy

4.1 Product Selection

Our criteria for selecting products are:

1. Grocery items are available across many major supermarkets.
2. Products must be available in at least two different package sizes of the same brand, and there must be no difference in features between products except for size (for example, a squeeze bottle for tomato sauce compared to a can of tomato sauce).

The sample of products deemed to fit this criterion is in the *attached Appendix (Excel file)*.

4.2 Store Selection

Our criteria for selecting stores are:

1. Nationwide presence with online pricing available.
2. Located in either a 'RichNeighbourhood' or 'PoorNeighbourhood'. I define a 'PoorNeighbourhood' to be where Median Total Household Income in the store suburb is below \$70,000 and the average NZ Deprivation score falls within the top 20% nationally (i.e., indicating high deprivation). I define a 'RichNeighbourhood' to be where Median Total Household Income in the store suburb is above \$124,000 and the average NZ Deprivation score falls within the bottom 20% nationally (i.e., indicating low deprivation).

Exclude:

- Stores located in CBDs, airports, or large shopping centres are excluded to ensure that the store location reflects the socioeconomic characteristics of shoppers.

In order to obtain our selection of stores, we followed the following steps:

- Step 1 - Extract NZDep scores¹, which provide an indicator for neighbourhood deprivation. The data is available for small geographical areas of Statistical Area 1 (SA1), but as this study focuses on residential suburbs, it will utilise a more aggregated level of data at the SA3 level. To determine the neighbourhood suburb at the SA3 level,

¹ NZ Deprivation Scores sourced from University of Otago research:
<https://www.otago.ac.nz/wellington/research/groups/research-groups-in-the-department-of-public-health/hirp/socioeconomic-deprivation-indexes-nzdep-and-nzidep-department-of-public-health>

we average the NZDep indicators across SA1, to form the average SA3 level indicator. We rank the neighbourhoods by quintiles and focus only on the top 20% (high deprivation, or poorer) and bottom 20% (low deprivation, or richer).

- Step 2 – Find the population of PaknSave, New World and Woolworths NZ stores in New Zealand, by reviewing 'store finder' on the respective websites and collecting information on each store in an Excel spreadsheet, documenting the supermarket chain, the street address of the store, suburb (SA3), and whether the store is in a CBD, shopping centre, airport location and should be excluded.
- Step 3 - Identify the income measures for the corresponding SA3 suburbs:
 - Determine whether the stores fall in a Rich Neighbourhood or a Poor Neighbourhood, based on the NZDep quintiles in Step 1.
 - Determine the Median Total Household Income for the store suburbs². Incomes above \$124,000 were considered to be richer, and incomes below \$70,000 were considered to be poorer.

Result: We have compiled a list of 19 stores located in a neighbourhood deemed as a 'Rich Neighbourhood' and 21 stores located in a neighbourhood deemed as a 'Poor Neighbourhood'. The stores on each of these lists have been randomly sorted. The list of stores is available in the *attached Appendix*.

4.3 Product Data Collection Approach

Data collection will begin with the first store on the (randomly sorted) rich-neighbourhood list, where we will collect data on all available items from our list of 50 product types. We will then move to the first store on the (randomly sorted) poor-neighbourhood list, and alternate between rich and poor neighbourhoods until we reach the target sample size.

In each supermarket, we will record the following for each product: product name, package size, total price, unit price, date and time of data collection, and any relevant comments.

² Median Total Household Income for SA3 suburbs sourced through Infometrics:
<https://rep.infometrics.co.nz/wellington-city/census/drill-down/total-household-income/median-household-income?compare=new-zealand&census=lyall-bay-sa3-2023>

5. Pilot and Power Analysis

Based on a power analysis (see Appendix) using pilot data collected from one high-income neighbourhood (Ponsonby) and one low-income neighbourhood (Greymouth) - both outside the richest and poorest quintiles - we determined that approximately 656 surcharge or discount instances are required to achieve adequate statistical power (80%) to detect a 10 percentage point difference. This corresponds to approximately 1,350 product-size-store observations.

We plan to sample 50 commonly available grocery products across at least 27 supermarkets, with approximately balanced distribution in both Rich and Poor neighbourhoods. Once the target of 1,350 product-store observations is reached, data collection for the remaining products in that store will be completed, and then data collection will cease.

6. Pre-Registration Statement

This registration includes all key hypotheses and models. Any additional analyses (e.g., descriptive or exploratory robustness checks) will be transparently flagged as post hoc in final reporting. We commit to reporting all results and not selectively reporting based on statistical significance.

References

- Binkley, J. K., & Bejnarowicz, J. (2003). Consumer price awareness in food shopping: The case of quantity surcharges. *Journal of Retailing*, 27-35.
- Goel, D. G. (2024). Quantity surcharge, competition and package size: Evidence from India. *Journal of Revenue and Pricing Management*, 23(5), 452–460.
- Sprott, D. E., Manning, K. C., & Miyazaki, A. D. (2003). Grocery price setting and quantity surcharges. *Journal of Marketing*, 67 (3), 34–46.